

Original Research

Realizing the Threshold Effect of Trade Openness in Finance-FDI Nexus: Evidence from Belt and Road Initiative Countries

Mollah Aminul Islam¹

Department of Accounting & Information Systems, Jatiya Kabi Kazi Nazrul Islam University, Mymensingh, Bangladesh

Md. Miraj Hossen

Department of Management, Jagannath University, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Received 31 January 2025 Revised 3 May 2025 Accepted 24 May 2025

Abstract

A country's attitude towards cross-border trade and its level of openness exert a significant effect on inward foreign direct investment (FDI) flows, which is yet to be empirically answered. Thus, this study explores how trade openness moderates the effect of financial development on FDI inflows in BRI countries, with an emphasis on threshold effects. The panel threshold estimator shows a single significant threshold of 4.524 (or 92.241%) of financial development units, above which the relationship between FD-FDI turns nonlinear. It implies that FD may positively attract FDI when a country achieves a trade openness (TO) beyond a certain threshold level while below the said threshold level, FD may not attract FDI convincingly. The threshold identified indicates a moderate level of TO. The results are robust under different proxies and sub-samples. Thus, the policymakers are suggested to enhance the financial system and concentrate on maintaining a minimum level of TO while devising policies to attract FDI.

Keywords: BRI, FDI, Financial Development, GMM, PTM, Trade Openness.

¹ Corresponding author's Email: onlinedu@gmail.com

Introduction

The neoclassical theory identifies the importance of foreign direct investment (FDI) in economic gains through capital formation (reinvestment and new inflow of capital) in host countries (Saini & Singhania, 2018). FDI is most often considered to be a transfer package that includes technology, technical know-how, and management capacity from developed to developing world (Islam et al., 2019; Islam et al., 2018; Liu et al., 2020) to achieve sustainable development (Islam et al., 2020). Those transfers benefit the country through spillover effects, go beyond the monetary transaction flows and account for all transfers of tangibles (e.g., machinery) and intangibles (e.g., patent, management capacity, technical knowledge, etc.) that accompany FDI projects from home to host country. These improve the host country's productivity and efficiency, leading to greater profitability. Thus, it is essential to search for the vital issues that constitute a country's attractiveness to host FDI projects, considering the immense importance of FDI for sustainable real economic output. Nowadays, countries are striving to attract FDI (Desbordes & Wei, 2017) by undertaking different policy formulations and modifications. However, some countries are remaining less attractive as FDI destinations in comparison to other countries. Hence, the question remains, why?

Literature (for example, Islam et al., 2020; Liu et al., 2020) supports that gaining sustainable benefits from FDI is positively associated with financial development (hereafter, FD). FD delivers a symbol of trust to the potential MNCs (Islam et al., 2019; Islam et al., 2018) and is considered an excellent external source of finance (Desbordes & Wei, 2017) to accommodate their upfront fixed costs. Many researchers acknowledged that MNCs often strive to list their stocks in local stock markets² to satisfy their capital needs which may reduce the cost of capital (Islam, Liu, et al., 2021). Moreover, the spillover benefits of FDI in the forms of technology diffusion are realizable for economic progress only when the financial sector development overcomes a threshold point (Choong, 2012; Liu et al., 2020). This means that countries with a weak financial system are unpopular destinations for MNCs.

On the other hand, researchers found that different cross-border trade openness mechanisms ensure more FDI inflows. For example, regional trade agreements (Liu, 2008) and trade liberalization in terms of tariff reductions (Kandilov et al., 2019) significantly increase the FDI inflows. Thus, satisfactory FD may still fail to attract substantial FDI if trade openness (hereafter, TO) mechanisms are lacking. Variations in TO may, therefore, differentially impact the FD-FDI relationship. The absorptive capacity expected from the development of financial sector and incoming FDI projects is not achieved instantaneously. It is achieved only when the external environment, more specifically, TO is achieved. This can be justified as FDI is a cross-border issue which is highly connected to TO. It ensures linkages between domestic markets and global value chains which motivate financial sector to be more effective to allocate finances into productive sectors and enhance their attractiveness to foreign investors. TO is a multinational issue which may more often have a complex impact on economic factors (Liargovas & Skandalis, 2012). A country, with a developed financial sector but low TO

² Stock and bond markets are contended as one of the two major parts of financial system.

may face struggles due to comparatively infrequent cross-border activities, regulatory inefficiency and resulting investor confidence gaps (Jena & Sethi, 2021).

On the other hand, investors of an open economy may enjoy low-cost financing as domestic capital markets are better integrated into cross-border capital movements. The interrelation among financial development, trade openness and FDI justifies the existence of a threshold effect of TO in catalyzing FD to attract FDI inflows. The financial sector development comprising two major components-financial institutions and financial markets, requires ensuring appropriate environment to gain attractiveness for FDI, which can be achieved by ensuring higher trade openness. The desired environment in case of FD-FDI connection can be ensured by trade openness (Islam et al., 2020), since it acts as an amplifier of the power of financial sector to attract FDI from foreign investors (Cantah et al., 2018; Liu et al., 2020). There may be different other factors which also catalyze the issue, such as human capital of the FDI host country, its macroeconomic achievements (Nkoa, 2018), macroeconomic stability (Kamal et al., 2019), physical and digital infrastructure (Otchere et al., 2016), domestic investment (Farla et al., 2016) and market size (Kutan et al., 2017) etc. The role of TO in the FD-FDI connection is under addressed in literature to date. The conceptual issue can be explained in a framework as below:

Figure 1: The conceptual framework

The study strategically extends existing literature in multiple ways. Firstly, it analyses the threshold effect of TO in FD-FDI connection by using a panel threshold model. The study also considers the endogeneity issues using the two-step system GMM. Secondly, unlike traditional measures, this study uses the most comprehensive proxy of FD (Khan, Islam, et al., 2020; Khan et al., 2019; Liu et al., 2020) in determining the threshold effect of TO on the effect of FD on FDI inflows. Finally, the study further analyses the relations under consideration using financial market and financial institution development (FMD and FID, respectively) as two dimensions of financial system (Khan, Islam, et al., 2020). A very few studies provide fundamental insights focusing on the direct effect of FD on FDI while TO is largely considered as a separate independent variable (for example, Cantah et al., 2018; Liargovas & Skandalis, 2012). In contrast, the current study innovatively investigates the threshold effect in FD-FDI connection, considering a nonlinear approach. Drawing on the institutional FDI fitness theory, this study posits that beyond a certain threshold of trade openness (TO), countries may experience enhanced benefits from financial development (FD) in attracting foreign direct investment (FDI), primarily through mechanisms such as increased investor confidence and trust, reduced transaction costs, and more efficient capital allocation.

Moreover, the current study considers partner countries of the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) as a study sample. The BRI is a step toward regional development (Cheng, 2016) initiated by the Chinese President. The BRI partners are increasingly becoming known as a new group of countries that aims for mutual connectivity and cooperation (Liu et al., 2020; Soong, 2016). The countries are diverged in development characteristics, culture and location, which covers a population of more than 65% of the world (Liu et al., 2020; Rauf et al., 2018). These countries together constitute a major driving force of economic growth (Aibai et al., 2019).

The empirical results are driven in two steps. Firstly, the impact of FD on FDI is explored using the comprehensive and some frequently used traditional proxies of FDI. Secondly, the existence of threshold impact is analyzed. The results show that irrespective of proxies and methodologies, FD exerts a significant and positive influence on FDI inflows. Moreover, as an FD proxy, the Financial Development Index (FDx) best explain the impact of FD to attract FDI.

Furthermore, we find the existence of a statistically viable single threshold of TO (92.241) in the FD-FDI connection. It means that a country should attain at least this level of TO to use FD in efficiently attracting FDI. Based on the identified threshold value point, a split sample analysis has been conducted where we find a significant incremental effect of FD in attracting FDI in a high TO regime, whereas the effect is insignificant and/or negative in a low TO regime. Our robustness checks based on segment FD (into FMD and FID) reveal a very consistent and reliable finding.

The second section of this paper discusses the materials and methods of our study . The empirical results have been reported in the third section, followed by results and discussions in the fourth section. Finally, the fifth section presents recommendations for academia, investors and policymakers and concludes the paper.

Materials and Methods

This research explores the ability of FD to attract FDI in a sustainable way and the role of TO levels in FD-FDI connection. It leads us to use the (inward FDI measured as ‘stock of FDI’) as the dependent variable (Islam et al., 2020; Liu et al., 2020; Sachs, 2018) which represents the cumulating effect (Cheng & Kwan, 2000) of FDI of the host country. We consider FD to be the key independent variable. We follow recent literature on relevant issues (for example, Hassan et al., 2016; Islam et al., 2020; Islam, Liu, et al., 2021; Khan, Islam, et al., 2020; Liu et al., 2020; Sultanuzzaman et al., 2019; Yahia et al., 2018) and control for other important variables such as human capital (HC), real GDP (RGDP), macroeconomic stability or inflation (INF), trade openness (TO) infrastructure (INFR), domestic investment (DI) and population (Pop). We control one-year lag effect of the dependent variable as well. Thus, the functional form of the relation takes the equation as below:

$$FDI_{it} = f(FDI_{i,t-1}, FD_{it}, HC_{it}, RGDP_{it}, INFL_{it}, TO_{it}, INFR_{it}, DI_{it}, Pop_{it}) \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

The variables other than those in indexes and percentages are transformed into logarithmic form. Thus, the empirical model takes the form of equation (2) as below:

$$\ln FDI_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln FDI_{i,t-1} + \beta_2 FDx_{it} + \beta_3 \ln HC_{it} + \beta_4 \ln RGDPpc_{it} + \beta_5 \ln INF_{it} + \beta_6 \ln TO_{it} + \beta_7 INFR_{it} + \beta_8 \ln DI_{it} + \beta_9 \ln Pop_{it} + \mu_{it} \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Where $\ln FDI_{it}$ represents inward FDI and $\ln FDI_{i,t-1}$ measures the initial FDI of the same country, FDx_{it} represents the proxies of financial development and $\ln HC_{it}$ represents human capital (Cleeve et al., 2015; Nkoa, 2018) proxied by labor participation rate; $\ln RGDPpc_{it}$ represents real GDP per capita, constant as of 2010 (Al Nasser & Gomez, 2009; Hossain et al., 2022; Otchere et al., 2016); INF_{it} represents inflation proxied by consumer price index (Aibai et al., 2019; Kamal et al., 2019; Miniesy & Elish, 2017), $\ln TO_{it}$ represents a country's attitude of openness to cross border trade, measured as the ratio of total export and import to GDP (Cantah et al., 2018; Kutan et al., 2017), $INFR_{it}$ measures infrastructure of the country proxied by fixed telephone lines per 100 people (Nkoa, 2018); the domestic investment, $\ln DI_{it}$, is measured by gross fixed capital formation (Farla et al., 2016; Islam, Liu, et al., 2021) and $\ln Pop_{it}$ measures the size of the market proxied by total population (Agbloyor et al., 2014; Agbloyor et al., 2016; Kutan et al., 2017; Majeed et al., 2023). The β s represent the coefficients of the relevant variables, i and t stand for country and time period respectively. μ represents the white noise generated from country and time specific errors.

One of the major challenges of the current study is to find the most appropriate or relevant proxy for FD. Researchers allowed different activity-based indicators to proxy for FD. In the current study, FD is represented by the Financial Development Index (FDx) originally developed by the IMF in a staff meeting (Islam, Hossain, et al., 2021; Sahay et al., 2016; Svirydenka, 2016). This index is considered as the most reasonable and reliable proxy (Islam, Das, et al., 2021; Islam et al., 2018; Khan & Khan, 2019) to represent the financial sector which accounts for both financial markets and financial institutions. We additionally consider several frequently practiced traditional Finance proxies to support our analysis, such as quasi money and supply of money as a percentage share of GDP, M2 (Adjasi et al., 2012; Agbloyor et al., 2014; Choong & Lim, 2009; Hussain & Haque, 2017; Kutan et al., 2017; Nkoa, 2018; Rousseau & Wachtel, 2011), domestic credit provided to private sector by banks (Agbloyor et al., 2014; Kutan et al., 2017; Silva et al., 2017), domestic credit provided to the private sector in ratio to GDP (Islam et al., 2019; Islam et al., 2020; Tzeremes, 2018), liquid liabilities (Hajilee & Al Nasser, 2015; Kaur et al., 2013; Levine, 1997; Otchere et al., 2016; Soumaré & Tchana Tchana, 2015), and financial system deposits (Islam et al., 2020; Liu et al., 2020). For the sake of consistency with relevant literature, we controlled for important economic and financial issues such as, trade openness (Cantah et al., 2018; Fan et al., 2018; Kutan et al., 2017), domestic investment (Gross fixed capital formation (Farla et al., 2016; Yahia et al., 2018)), human capital (labour participation rate as per ILO estimates (Liu et al., 2020)), Gross Domestic Product per capita (Otchere et al., 2016), inflation (consumer price index using the base year 2010 (Kamal et al., 2019)), the total population of the country which measures the market size of the economy (Agbloyor et al., 2016; Kutan et al., 2017), and infrastructural development (proxied by fixed telephone line number, per hundred people (Al Nasser & Gomez, 2009)). The FDI data is collected from UNCTAD (2024), FDx data comes from the IMF (2024) and data for other variables are extracted from WDI (2024). Data from 2004 to 2022 for a (Hossen, Islam, & Raihanul, 2021; Islam, 2021b) BRI network countries (see Appendix B) have been used. The selection of country

sample was entirely based on data availability. From the broader pool of data, we omitted the countries and series with high levels of missing values to ensure a consistent panel of BRI sample countries. It resulted in retention of 79 countries in the sample. As no other selection or exclusion criteria was used, the resulting sample is expected to be free from biases and deliver a diverse representation of BRI countries and provide meaningful insight in this research.

Estimation Strategy

To investigate the potential nonlinearity, we analyze the threshold effect of TO in the FD-FDI relationship utilizing the panel threshold model (PTM) developed by Hansen (1999). PTM gives us a systematic procedure to trace the turning point in the relation (Liu et al., 2020), which helps decision-makers in policy formulation. Therefore, as guided by the recent literature (Abdulahi et al., 2019; Huang et al., 2018; Khan, Popp, et al., 2020; Liu et al., 2020), the model for a single threshold for our case is defined as below:

$$FD_{i,t} = \begin{cases} \hat{c}_i + \alpha_1 X_{i,t} + \beta_1 \check{v}_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t}, & \check{v}_i < \gamma \\ \hat{c}_i + \alpha_2 X_{i,t} + \beta_2 \check{v}_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t}, & \check{v}_i \geq \gamma \end{cases} \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

Where \hat{c}_i represents the fixed effects; X represents the vector consisting of independent regressors; \check{v} is the threshold variable; i is the cross-section (country) and t is the year; α_1 and α_2 are the coefficients for the independent variables whereas β_1 and β_2 are the same for the threshold variables.

In case a higher threshold is found in the relation, it can be generally modelled as below:

$$FD_{i,t} = \begin{cases} \hat{c}_i + \alpha_1 X_{i,t} + \beta_1 \check{v}_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t}, & \check{v}_{i,t} < \gamma_1 \\ \hat{c}_i + \alpha_2 X_{i,t} + \beta_2 \check{v}_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t}, & \gamma_1 \leq \check{v}_{i,t} < \gamma_2 \\ \hat{c}_i + \alpha_3 X_{i,t} + \beta_3 \check{v}_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t}, & \check{v}_{i,t} \geq \gamma_2 \end{cases} \dots \dots \dots (4)$$

where α_3 and β_3 are coefficients for independent and threshold variables and γ_1 and γ_2 are different threshold points identified in the analysis.

Due to suspected endogeneity caused by reverse causality in FD-FDI relations (Hanif & Shariff, 2016), we apply the GMM estimator (Hasan et al., 2020) developed by Arellano and Bover (1995), which deals with moment conditions. In the current case, we have a panel data with a larger cross-sectional units, N (79) and fewer time periods, T (19), which is also suitable for GMM. In the cases where the model suffers from endogeneity bias and the majority of instruments are not confidently exogenous, GMM works better to resolve the issues by adding moment conditions. The system GMM estimator is considered to be more efficient than the difference GMM (Bond, 2002) while endogeneity and fixed effect issues exist. According to Soto (2009), the system GMM estimator is prone to low bias and higher efficiency in comparison to difference GMM and other estimators. Moreover, the two-step system GMM is more efficient and largely used in economic studies (Islam & Islam, 2022; Sultanuzzaman et al., 2019), especially for a panel data analysis. GMM is consistent with heteroscedasticity, autocorrelation, endogeneity, and omitted variable bias (Kamal et al., 2019; Rahman et al., 2017). It is

also suitable and frequently used in macroeconomic studies (for example, Islam et al., 2020; Saini & Singhania, 2018; Sultanuzzaman et al., 2019).

In macroeconomic studies with a large panel of countries, the issue with cross-sectional dependency is commonly observed. This is another reason for using GMM technique in the study. The approach is especially valid while the time dimension is smaller than cross sections. The GMM technique uses second-order moment restrictions to be imposed on the covariance matrix of $\alpha \gamma_i + \mu_i$ where $\gamma = (\gamma_1 \dots \dots \gamma_T)'$ and $\mu = (\mu_{i1} \dots \dots \mu_{iT})'$ (Sarafidis & Wansbeek, 2012). The method is recognized in economic literature in presence of cross-sectional dependency (Haque, 2020) which creates consistent and reliable estimations.

Furthermore, due to the suspected presence of cross-sectional dependency, we utilize Driscoll and Kraay (1998) standard error estimation technique (hereafter, DK). DK standard technique accounts for cross-sectional dependency using the mean values of product of explanatory variables and residuals. The values are then used as weights to estimate Heteroscedasticity- and autocorrelation-consistent (HAC) standard errors which is considered as efficient to deal with cross-sectional dependence (Baloch et al., 2019). Thus, the DK standard error technique is appropriate for dealing with temporal and cross-sectional dependency (Ahmad et al., 2020; Khan, Islam, et al., 2020).

However, to check the threshold effects, the data is divided into two different regimes based upon the identified threshold- namely, above threshold and below threshold regimes. To make a better confirmation of threshold effects, we additionally utilize fixed and random effect estimators (one to be selected based on the Hausman test) to check the robustness. As FE/RE models are prone to heteroscedasticity and serial correlations, we use the Driscoll-Kraay estimator (Driscoll & Kraay, 1998) for robust standard errors.

Results and Discussions

The study considers the threshold effect of TO in actualizing the impact of FD on FDI in BRI countries. This section presents the analysis results Our detailed empirical exercise finds the TO have significant threshold impact in FD-FDI connection. TO have robustness of findings we subdivide the country level data as below the threshold level and above the threshold level and reanalyzed the impact. We find consistent results across sub-samples and estimations strategies.

Descriptive Statistics and Correlation Matrix

Table 1 presents summary statistics of the variables under analysis which includes the number of observations, mean, standard deviation, and minimum and maximum values. As is evident from the table, the number of observations, in most of the cases, is 1501. We find the mean value of FDI to be 23.135 with a standard deviation of 2.157. The key independent variable, FDx (an index ranging from 0 to 1), has a mean value of 0.549 with a standard deviation of 0.161. The threshold variable TO has a mean value of 4.371 with a standard deviation of 0.449. The table also contains the summary of other variables including alternative traditional proxies of FD.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics of the Variables

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
lnFDI	1501	23.135	2.157	15.302	28.03
FDx	1501	.549	.161	.173	.927
FMx	1501	.409	.256	0	.949
FIx	1501	.63	.141	.243	.96
lnHC	1501	7.446	.791	5.532	9.371
lnRGDPpc	1501	8.508	1.274	5.613	11.048
lnINFL	1465	4.48	.345	2.587	5.82
lnDI	1488	9.743	1.81	.009	17.807
lnTO	1498	4.371	.449	3.031	6.09
INFR	1498	3.833	1.871	.27	8.081
lnPop	1501	16.183	1.71	11.489	21.05
LO	1216	3.761	1.128	1	6
DCP	1456	50.807	35.624	.186	160.125
DCPB	1469	47.935	32.821	.186	159.764
M2	1356	61.119	38.822	6.724	257.946
LL	1486	10.003	2.255	4.359	16.951
FSD	1486	47.377	33.439	1.983	239.519

Note: Here, FDI = Inward Foreign Direct Investment, FDx = Financial Development Index, FMx = Financial Market Development Index, FIx = Financial Institution Development index, HC = Human Capital, RGDPpc = GDP per capita (2010 constant prices), INFL = Inflation, DI= Domestic Investment, TO = Trade Openness, INFR = Infrastructure, Pop= Total Population, LO = Law and Order, DCP = Domestic credit to private sector (% of GDP), DCPB = Domestic credit to the private sector by banks (% of GDP), M2 = Broad Money, LL = Liquid liabilities to GDP (%), FSD = Financial System Deposit in ratio to GDP. Source: Authors' Computations.

Properties and Correlation Between Main Variables

The correlation matrix (Pearson's pairwise) is presented in Table 2. This table shows that our key explanatory and explained variables, FDx and FDI, respectively, have a significant and strong positive correlation (0.523, $p < 0.001$). Furthermore, suppose the other values of the second column are concentrated. In that case, we see that our control variables also show a significant correlation with the explained variable at a 1 percent level ($p < 0.001$). Also, the values of the third column show that the explanatory and control variables do not have high correlations, although the existing correlations are significant. Thus, there is a very low chance of multicollinearity (Gujarati & Porter, 2009; Rahman et al., 2017).

Table 2. Correlation Between Main Variables

	lnFDI	FDx	lnHC	lnRGDPpc	lnINFL	lnDI	lnTO	INFR	lnPop
lnFDI	1								
FDx	0.523***	1							
lnHC	0.0767***	-0.0663**	1						
lnRGDPpc	0.370***	0.698***	0.110***	1					
lnINFL	0.188***	0.149***	0.00192	0.0898***	1				
lnDI	0.204***	0.0963***	0.103***	-0.0674**	-	1			
lnTO	0.165***	0.228***	0.166***	0.281***	-	0.150***	1		
INFR	0.304***	0.678***	-	0.667***	0.0197	0.0619**	0.172***	1	
lnPop	0.473***	0.0966***	0.166***	-0.144***	0.0331	0.340***	-0.191***	-0.0655**	1

* $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.

Role of FD to Attract FDI

Due to potential endogeneity in the FD-FDI issue (Hossen, Islam, & Begum, 2021; Islam, 2021a; Islam et al., 2020), we use GMM to estimate the relations. The results in GMM of the overall sample of 79 countries of the BRI have been presented in Table 3. The presented results show that traditional and new measures of FD, e.g., M2, DCPB, DCP, LL, FSD, and FDx have a significant ($p < 0.01$) and positive influence on the dependent variable (lnFDI), which implies that financial development of the host countries can allure foreign capital. Interestingly, it is found that human capital shows significant but negative coefficients. We additionally estimated the models with life expectancy, one of the frequently used human capital proxies, where we found a similar result (the results are not reported but available upon request). This can be explained by the lack of skilled labor. A similar negative association between HC and FDI is observed in prior literature, especially in developing countries where educational systems are still traditional and not aligned with the market demand created by the FDI projects hosted by the countries. Therefore, human development initiatives such as education and training outcomes have not gained productive capacity (Asteriou & Agiomirgianakis, 2001; Noorbakhsh et al., 2001). Nkoa (2018) found a similar adverse effect in a study on African countries and Liu et al. (2020) in BRI countries. In such cases, a developed human capital base does not always represent the availability of the types of skilled labors as required by foreign investors. Following Nkoa (2018), it can be argued that investors are likely to import skilled laborers from abroad if they are not satisfied enough with the quality of the existing labor force of the host country.

Table 3. Role of FD to Attract FDI- System GMM Results.

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
FDx	1.635*** (0.592)					
M2		0.003*** (0.001)				
DCP			0.007*** (0.001)			

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
DCPB				0.006***		
				(0.001)		
LL					0.973***	
					(0.086)	
FSD						0.012***
						(0.002)
l.lnFDI	0.088***	0.078***	0.069***	0.069***	0.065***	0.033***
	(0.014)	(0.017)	(0.012)	(0.012)	(0.013)	(0.009)
lnHC	0.013	-0.034	-0.029	-0.030	0.069	0.020
	(0.031)	(0.043)	(0.042)	(0.045)	(0.060)	(0.043)
lnRGDPpc	0.682***	0.864***	0.820***	0.818***	-0.269**	0.745***
	(0.060)	(0.039)	(0.031)	(0.037)	(0.111)	(0.049)
lnINFL	0.388***	0.293***	0.374***	0.336***	0.091	0.369***
	(0.057)	(0.078)	(0.083)	(0.088)	(0.108)	(0.068)
lnDI	-0.004	-0.018*	0.002	-0.001	-0.047***	-0.004
	(0.010)	(0.011)	(0.008)	(0.008)	(0.012)	(0.010)
lnTO	0.727***	0.735***	0.679***	0.678***	0.592***	0.608***
	(0.061)	(0.076)	(0.068)	(0.073)	(0.064)	(0.065)
INFR	0.080***	0.075**	0.033	0.032	0.089***	0.093***
	(0.023)	(0.029)	(0.027)	(0.028)	(0.031)	(0.025)
lnPop	0.776***	0.849***	0.821***	0.834***	-0.164	0.870***
	(0.028)	(0.023)	(0.023)	(0.023)	(0.101)	(0.022)
Cons	-3.309***	-4.168***	-3.544***	-3.127***	13.741***	-2.965***
	(0.874)	(0.713)	(0.721)	(0.726)	(2.470)	(0.625)
Obs.	1455	1310	1410	1423	1440	1442
Year Dummy	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Post						
AR1	0.66	1.18	1.14	0.91	0.66	1.86
P-value	0.507	0.236	0.256	0.365	0.512	0.062
AR2	0.42	0.40	0.61	0.47	1.10	0.55
P-value	0.675	0.687	0.543	0.637	0.271	0.582
Sargan test	488.74	394.51	427.01	0.637	251.26	409.07
P-value	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Hansen test	55.76	53.60	60.95	61.85	57.80	53.91
P-value	0.409	0.490	0.240	0.216	0.337	0.478

Note: Standard errors are in parenthesis; *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1.

The Threshold Effect of Trade Openness

An attitude of openness towards cross-border trade can significantly influence FDI inflow (Cantah et al., 2018) while the relationship is not so simple (Liargovas & Skandalis, 2012). The potential influence of TO remains in the FD-FDI relationship which posits the importance of analysing the nonlinearity effects. Thus, we tend to investigate the possible existence of nonlinearity caused by TO in this relationship. For this purpose, we use it as a threshold variable and deploy the panel threshold model (PTM) developed by Hansen (1999). We use the bootstrapping method (Hansen, 1999) and follow Liu et al. (2020) to construct a confidence interval. Bootstrapping also allows us to assess the significance level of identified threshold points (Abdulahi et al., 2019).

We attempt to identify the existence of single and double threshold levels in the relations and find only a single significant threshold at 5% level of significance, while double thresholds are found to be statistically insignificant (the results are presented in Table 4 and Fig. 1). The identified threshold value of logged TO is 4.524, which is equal to 92.241 in terms of real value with 500 bootstrap repetition (Liu et al., 2020). The result is consistent with a double bootstrap repetition. The results are presented in Table 5. These imply that a country should strive to be open (in terms of export and import in ratio to GDP) more than 92.241% to reap the benefits of financial development in attracting FDIs as the marginal effect of financial development beyond this level changes significantly for BRI sample. This level of trade openness is a moderate one because many open countries like Malaysia, Thailand and Vietnam report TO over 100% while less open economy of the sample like Bangladesh, Pakistan etc. often report around 30-40% of TO (WDI, 2024). As per our robust baseline findings, the higher the FD level a country achieves, the higher it will be attractive to MNCs as their potential investment destination. The findings suggest that financial development alone may not be sufficient to attract FDI significantly in countries unless the economy is well integrated to cross-border trade.

Table 4. Threshold Effect Test Estimations

	Threshold (<i>TO</i>)	
	Single	Double
F-stat	54.01	15.82
P-value	0.0300	0.5600
Critical values		
10%	38.6642	33.7283
5%	45.8552	40.2292
1%	66.5776	56.5882
Bootstrap count	500	500

Table 5. Threshold Estimation

Threshold Variable	Threshold Values	95% Confidence Interval	
		Lower Value	Upper Value
lnTO	4.5244	4.5158	4.5306

Fig 1. Confidence Level Construction for a Single Threshold Model. Source: Authors

A Split Sample Analysis to Realize the Threshold Effects

After identification of the threshold point for TO, we split the data into above and below threshold regimes and re-estimate the basic model along with some other estimators such as Fixed Effect (selected based upon Hausman test, please see Appendix A), and Driscoll and Kraay (DK) standard error. The results are presented in Table 6. The odd columns show the effect in the below threshold regime, while the even columns represent the same in the above threshold regime. The FE estimations show an insignificant effect of FD in attracting FDI in the below threshold regime while the above threshold regime has a significant positive impact. However, due to the potential presence of heteroscedasticity, cross-sectional dependence and serial correlation in FE models, we go for DK in addition to GMM. We find that DK is also proving consistent estimations. GMM estimations are presented in column 5 and 6. In the below threshold regime (column 5), we find a negative and significant result, whereas the significant and positive association is revealed in the above threshold regime (column 6). All these confirm our theoretical intuition that the impact of FD to attract FDI is affected by the level of TO achieved by an economy. In the other sense, FD of an economy attracts FDI only when the country possesses an open attitude towards cross-border trade.

Table 6. Role of Financial Development to Attract FDI-Analyzing Threshold Effect Based on the Split Sample

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
	FE	FE	DK	DK	GMM	GMM
FDx	0.574 (0.741)	2.714** (1.092)	0.574 (0.511)	2.714*** (0.563)	-5.447*** (1.107)	3.463*** (1.045)
l.lnFDI					0.104*** (0.028)	0.127** (0.057)
lnHC	0.197 (0.213)	0.013 (0.186)	0.197** (0.070)	0.013 (0.146)	-0.088 (0.108)	0.015 (0.094)
lnRGDPpc	0.447 (0.322)	0.846* (0.436)	0.447 (0.268)	0.846*** (0.257)	1.421*** (0.125)	0.465*** (0.115)
lnINFL	0.394*** (0.148)	1.063*** (0.290)	0.394*** (0.028)	1.063*** (0.171)	0.271 (0.178)	0.779*** (0.185)
lnDI	0.069** (0.029)	0.062*** (0.021)	0.069*** (0.018)	0.062*** (0.020)	-0.002 (0.020)	0.015 (0.027)
lnTO	0.053 (0.250)	0.025 (0.270)	0.053 (0.096)	0.025 (0.102)	0.504*** (0.145)	0.504** (0.202)
INFR	0.067 (0.050)	-0.147** (0.068)	0.067*** (0.022)	-0.147*** (0.046)	0.099* (0.054)	0.016 (0.053)
lnPop	0.690 (0.783)	1.058*** (0.381)	0.690 (0.708)	1.058*** (0.346)	0.994*** (0.043)	0.671*** (0.067)
Cons	3.975 (14.061)	-7.033 (9.449)	0.000 (0.000)	0.000 (0.000)	-7.335*** (2.056)	-2.384 (1.639)
Obs.	946	510	946	510	945	510

Note: Parenthesis contains standard errors; *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$.

Effect of FD in Attracting FDI- Robustness Checks Considering FMD, and FID Indices as an Alternative Estimator

In this section, we have checked the robustness of our model. To do that, we have taken FMx and Flx, two similar indexes of our original explanatory variable FDx representing financial market development (FMD) and financial institution development (FID). It is widely assumed that FMD and FID directly influence the financial development (FD) of a country (Islam et al., 2019; Islam et al., 2018; Liu et al., 2020). To justify the robustness of our model, we utilize a similar strategy used in baseline estimations, i.e., GMM. The results are presented in Table 7. The outcome of this robustness analysis reveals a remarkably consistent picture of our prior estimations. However, in the above threshold regime, FMx is showing an insignificant, though positive, coefficient. This may happen due to two main reasons. First, the financial markets of BRI partner countries are less developed, and second, FMx has zero (0) values in the dataset provided by the IMF which again indicates an underdeveloped status of the markets. Concerning Flx and other control variables, we find the results to be very consistent and in line with the theoretical judgments of the study. All these lead us to infer

that FD of a country can attract FDI significantly only when a country is open towards cross border trade, at least up to the threshold value.

Table 7. Role of FMD and FID to Attract FDI-Trade Openness Threshold Effects

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
FMx	-0.702 (0.507)	1.290 (0.778)		
Flx			-6.294*** (1.273)	2.039* (1.187)
l.lnFDI	0.113*** (0.025)	0.096** (0.040)	0.059*** (0.017)	0.131*** (0.047)
lnHC	0.040 (0.067)	-0.057 (0.085)	-0.049 (0.102)	0.052 (0.077)
lnRGDPpc	0.966*** (0.099)	0.513*** (0.134)	1.388*** (0.128)	0.589*** (0.106)
lnINFL	0.122 (0.100)	1.068*** (0.290)	0.304* (0.165)	1.010*** (0.324)
lnDI	-0.019 (0.016)	0.045* (0.025)	0.000 (0.024)	0.042 (0.029)
lnTO	0.498*** (0.118)	1.009*** (0.210)	0.767*** (0.145)	0.696** (0.284)
INFR	0.090** (0.035)	0.027 (0.060)	0.148*** (0.048)	0.007 (0.044)
lnPop	0.868*** (0.044)	0.687*** (0.095)	0.884*** (0.031)	0.733*** (0.073)
Cons	-4.411** (1.839)	-4.504 (2.933)	-6.462*** (1.459)	-6.346** (3.135)
Obs.	945	510	945	510
Year Dummy	YES	YES	YES	YES

Note: Standard errors are in parenthesis; *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$; The odd columns are for below threshold and even columns are for the above threshold regime.

According to Tables 3, 6 and 7, we find that estimations result from DK and GMM are highly consistent in terms of significance and sign of the coefficients. Thus, we argue that our results are robust and controlled for autocorrelation, heteroscedasticity, serial correlation and cross-sectional dependency. Therefore, the results are reliable for decision making purposes.

Conclusions and Policy Implications

The study investigates the ability of FD to attract and retain FDI, as this source of investment is largely viewed as a development ingredient for sustainable economic wellbeing. Furthermore, contemplating the importance of TO, the study uses it as a threshold variable in the connection of FD-FDI. We employ a novel index of FD promulgated by the IMF as a comprehensive measure of a multidimensional financial

system. Besides, the study also resorted to some other popularly used traditional measures of FD such as broad money, domestic credit provided to the private sector in GDP percentage, domestic credit provided by banks in GDP percentage, liquid liability in GDP percentage and financial system deposit in GDP percentage to cross verify the effect. The results depict that a developed financial sector can play a catalytic role to attract FDI.

The threshold estimator shows a single significant threshold of TO of 4.524, in logarithmic form (in real value equivalent to 92.241), above which FD may be beneficial for FDI. While below the said threshold level of TO, the FD negatively influences the FDI. This implies that when a country achieves this minimum threshold level of TO, it may reap the benefits of FD in stimulating the FDI. These findings have important implications for the stakeholders and policymakers. They not only have to concentrate on boosting the financial system but also have to maintain a minimum level of TO. The findings are robust in terms of methodological and dimensional (financial market and institution) differences.

The research has important policy implications. The policymakers of the region, especially those who want more FDI inflows, should follow the results of the research and generally concentrate to financial development of respective countries. Since FD is found to be an important influential factor to attract FDI, the policymakers should introduce policy-reforms to make the financial system well-functioning to attract more international capital inflow. The policymakers should prioritize trade-finance infrastructure and develop financial integration mechanisms across the corridors of BRI countries, such as a harmonization of financial regulations, settlement systems, cross-border transaction standards, digital trade facilitation, modern logistics infrastructure development and transparent reporting systems. These steps may broaden trade openness, facilitate capital mobilization and cost reduction, enhance investors' confidence and domestic absorptive capacity. These initiatives may navigate foreign direct investments to BRI countries. Moreover, the financial sector of a country should be as wide as possible and should include the widest public coverage so that people are encouraged to get connected to formal financial system. This will enable them to have access to funds. Such increased access to financial sector will develop the system and investors will be able to rely upon it. Thus, ensuring more creditworthiness, reliability, and accessibility of banking and non-banking financial services and the capital market for the foreign firms may attract foreign investors to BRI countries.

However, the research evidenced that TO plays a vital role in FD-FDI connection. Therefore, the policymakers, i.e. the political leadership should focus on more international collaborations. Such collaborations might be in the forms of free trade area, trade agreements, etc. Moreover, international knowledge sharing, technology exchanges, financial and non-financial integration and cooperating partnerships like BRI also can induce openness which, in turn, facilitate higher FDI attractiveness.

Moreover, as is evident from the research that human resources are having a weak significance in attracting FDI, policymakers should address the issue by assessing the human resources needs of MNC and should train their people accordingly. This will

increase the employability of people of the country. Moreover, the trained people will be attractive factors for MNCs.

However, this study does not accommodate different FDI motives and considers all types of inward FDI in aggregate to reveal the phenomena. Furthermore, different levels of human capital is not considered in this study. Future researchers may investigate the role of the subsectors of the economy as well as the distinguished constructs of FD to attract foreign investors. Moreover, future researchers may look into the issue in different skill levels, educational levels and sector-specific skilled labor readiness which can help formulate more specific policy guidelines for BRI countries.

References

- Abdulahi, M. E., et al. (2019). Resource rents, economic growth, and the role of institutional quality: A panel threshold analysis. *Resources Policy*, 61, 293-303, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resourpol.2019.02.011>
- Adjasi, C. K., et al. (2012). FDI and economic activity in Africa: The role of local financial markets. *Thunderbird International Business Review*, 54(4), 429-439, <https://doi.org/10.1002/tie.21474>
- Agbloyor, E. K., et al. (2014). Private capital flows and economic growth in Africa: The role of domestic financial markets. *Journal of International Financial Markets, Institutions and Money*, 30, 137-152, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intfin.2014.02.003>
- Agbloyor, E. K., et al. (2016). Foreign direct investment and economic growth in SSA: The role of institutions. *Thunderbird International Business Review*, 58(5), 479-497, <https://doi.org/10.1002/tie.21791>
- Ahmad, M., et al. (2020). Does financial development and foreign direct investment improve environmental quality? Evidence from belt and road countries. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research International*, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-020-08748-7>
- Aibai, A., et al. (2019). Foreign Direct Investment, Institutional Quality, and Financial Development along the Belt and Road: An Empirical Investigation. *Emerging Markets Finance and Trade*, 1-20, <https://doi.org/10.1080/1540496X.2018.1559139>
- Al Nasser, O. M., & Gomez, X. G. (2009). Do well-functioning financial systems affect the FDI flows to Latin America. *International Research Journal of Finance and Economics*, 29(July), 60-75, <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/292649478>
- Arellano, M., & Bover, O. (1995). Another look at the instrumental variable estimation of error-components models. *Journal of Econometrics*, 68(1), 29-51, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-4076\(94\)01642-D](https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-4076(94)01642-D)

- Asteriou, D., & Agiomirgianakis, G. M. (2001). Human capital and economic growth: time series evidence from Greece. *Journal of Policy Modeling*, 23(5), 481-489, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0161-8938\(01\)00054-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0161-8938(01)00054-0)
- Baloch, M. A., et al. (2019). The effect of financial development on ecological footprint in BRI countries: evidence from panel data estimation [journal article]. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 26(6), 6199-6208, <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-018-3992-9>
- Bond, S. R. (2002). Dynamic panel data models: a guide to micro data methods and practice. *Portuguese economic journal*, 1(2), 141-162, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10258-002-0009-9>
- Cantah, G. W., et al. (2018). FDI and Trade Policy Openness in Sub-Saharan Africa. *Eastern Economic Journal*, 44(1), 97-116, <https://doi.org/10.1057/ej.2016.9>
- Cheng, L. K. (2016). Three questions on China's "Belt and Road Initiative". *China Economic Review*, 40, 309-313, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chieco.2016.07.008>
- Cheng, L. K., & Kwan, Y. K. (2000). What are the determinants of the location of foreign direct investment? The Chinese experience. *Journal of international economics*, 51(2), 379-400, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-1996\(99\)00032-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-1996(99)00032-X)
- Choong, C.-K. (2012). Does domestic financial development enhance the linkages between foreign direct investment and economic growth? *Empirical Economics*, 42(3), 819-834, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00181-011-0455-2>
- Choong, C.-K., & Lim, K.-P. (2009). Foreign direct investment, financial development, and economic growth: the case of Malaysia. *Macroeconomics and Finance in Emerging Market Economies*, 2(1), 13-30, <https://doi.org/10.1080/17520840902726227>
- Cleeve, E. A., et al. (2015). Human Capital and FDI Inflow: An Assessment of the African Case. *World Development*, 74, 1-14, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2015.04.003>
- Desbordes, R., & Wei, S.-J. (2017). The effects of financial development on foreign direct investment. *Journal of Development Economics*, 127, 153-168, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdeveco.2017.02.008>
- Driscoll, J. C., & Kraay, A. C. (1998). Consistent covariance matrix estimation with spatially dependent panel data. *Review of economics and statistics*, 80(4), 549-560, <https://doi.org/10.1162/003465398557825>
- Fan, H., et al. (2018). The Impact of Trade, Technology and Growth on Environmental Deterioration of China and India. *Asian Economic and Financial Review*, 9(1), 1-29, <https://doi.org/10.18488/journal.aefr.2019.91.1.29>

- Farla, K., et al. (2016). Institutions, Foreign Direct Investment, and Domestic Investment: Crowding Out or Crowding In? *World Development*, 88, 1-9, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2014.04.008>
- Gujarati, D. N., & Porter, D. C. (2009). *Basic econometrics*. Tata McGraw-Hill Education. https://cbpbu.ac.in/userfiles/file/2020/STUDY_MAT/ECO/1.pdf
- Hajilee, M., & Al Nasser, O. M. (2015). The relationship between financial market development and foreign direct investment in Latin American countries. *The Journal of Developing Areas*, 49(2), 227-245, <https://doi.org/10.1353/jda.2015.0043>
- Hanif, A., & Shariff, S. S. M. (2016). Relationship Between Foreign Direct Investment and Financial Development. Proceedings of the 1st AAGBS International Conference on Business Management 2014 (AiCoBM 2014),
- Hansen, B. E. (1999). Threshold effects in non-dynamic panels: Estimation, testing, and inference. *Journal of Econometrics*, 93(2), 345-368, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-4076\(99\)00025-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-4076(99)00025-1)
- Haque, M. I. (2020). Oil price shocks and energy consumption in GCC countries: a system-GMM approach. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 1-16, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-020-01027-y>
- Hasan, M. R., et al. (2020). Operational efficiency effects of blockchain technology implementation in firms. *Review of International Business and Strategy*, <https://doi.org/10.1108/RIBS-05-2019-0069>
- Hassan, M. R., et al. (2016). Per Capita GDP And Population Growth Nexus: Facts from a Cross Country Analysis. *The Cost and Management*, 44(6), 39-43, <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/336317829>
- Hossain, M. I., et al. (2022). Does Foreign Aid have an Expected Role in the Economic Growth of Bangladesh? An Analysis in ARDL Approach. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Issues*, 12(6), 113-126, <https://doi.org/10.32479/ijefi.13664>
- Hossen, M. M., et al. (2021). Telehealth Services Acceptance Behaviour Among iGeneration of Bangladesh- An Application of Extended UTAUT Model. *The Jahangirnagar Journal of Business Studies*, 10(1), 233-243, <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/362032883>
- Hossen, M. M., et al. (2021). Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) and Bangladesh: Perceptions of Local Communities. *Jahangirnagar University Journal of Management Research*, 4, 47-63, https://jnu.ac.bd/journal/assets/pdf/13_3_637.pdf

- Huang, J., et al. (2018). The effect of technological factors on China's carbon intensity: New evidence from a panel threshold model. *Energy policy*, 115, 32-42, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2017.12.008>
- Hussain, M., & Haque, M. (2017). Fiscal Deficit and Its Impact on Economic Growth: Evidence from Bangladesh. *Economies*, 5(4), 37, <https://doi.org/10.3390/economies5040037>
- IMF. (2024). *Financial Development Index Database* (<http://data.imf.org/?sk=F8032E80-B36C-43B1-AC26-493C5B1CD33B>)
- Islam, M. A. (2021a). Classroom Efficiency in New Normal: Learning Satisfaction of Bangladeshi Public University Students. *Journal of Governance and Development*, 01(01), <https://jkkniu.edu.bd/wp-content/uploads/2023/07/Journal-of-GAD-Vol-1-Issue-1-Full-compressed.pdf>
- Islam, M. A. (2021b). Financial Development and FDI Nexus- Evidence from One Belt One Road Economies. *International Journal of Management, Accounting and Economics*, 8(7), 499-516, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5218894>
- Islam, M. A., et al. (2021). Financial Development and Foreign Direct Investment in Belt and Road Initiative Economies- the Moderating Effect of Human Capital. *The Cost and Management*, 49(01), 4-14, <http://www.icmab.org.bd/journal/january-february-2021/>
- Islam, M. A., et al. (2019). Financial Deepening, Foreign Direct Investment and Economic growth: an ARDL Approach Evidence from Bangladesh. *The Jahangirnagar Journal of Business Studies*, 8(1), 169-190, <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Mollah-Islam/publication/340248551>
- Islam, M. A., et al. (2021). Financial development and foreign direct investment nexus: A systematic review of literature. *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science* (2147-4478), 10(4), 226-238, <https://doi.org/10.20525/ijrbs.v10i4.121>
- Islam, M. A., et al. (2020). Financial Development and Foreign Direct Investment—The Moderating Role of Quality Institutions. *Sustainability*, 12(9), 3556, <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12093556>
- Islam, M. A., et al. (2021). Does foreign direct investment deepen the financial system in Southeast Asian economies? *Journal of Multinational Financial Management*, 100682, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mulfin.2021.100682>
- Islam, M. A., et al. (2018). Causal Relationship between Economic Growth, Financial Deepening, Foreign Direct Investment and Innovation: Evidence from China. *Asian Economic and Financial Review*, 8(8), 1086-1101, <https://doi.org/10.18488/journal.aefr.2018.88.1086.1101>

- Islam, M. T., & Islam, M. A. (2022). Dynamic Association Between Board Independence and Firm Profitability: The Moderating Role of Director Ownership. *Journal of Management and Economic Studies*, 4(3), 389-399, <https://doi.org/10.26677/TR1010.2022.1095>
- Jena, N. R., & Sethi, N. (2021). Foreign capital and growth nexus revisited: empirical evidence from South Asian countries. *Transnational Corporations Review*, 13(3), 269-292, <https://doi.org/10.1080/19186444.2020.1862602>
- Kamal, M. A., et al. (2019). Natural resource or market seeking motive of China's FDI in asia? New evidence at income and sub-regional level. *Economic Research-Ekonomska Istraživanja*, 32(1), 3869-3894, <https://doi.org/10.1080/1331677X.2019.1674679>
- Kandilov, I. T., et al. (2019). Trade Liberalization and Investment in Foreign Capital Goods: A Look at the Intensive Margin. *Emerging Markets Finance and Trade*, 1-24, <https://doi.org/10.1080/1540496X.2019.1694896>
- Kaur, M., et al. (2013). Financial system development and foreign direct investment: A panel data study for BRIC countries. *Global Business Review*, 14(4), 729-742, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0972150913501607>
- Khan, H., & Khan, U. (2019). Financial development and FDI inflows in China. *Economics Discussion Papers, No 2019-54, Kiel Institute for the World Economy*, <https://doi.org/http://www.economics-ejournal.org/economics/discussionpapers/2019-54>
- Khan, M. A., et al. (2020). Do economic freedom matters for finance in developing economies: a panel threshold analysis. *Applied Economics Letters*, 1-4, <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504851.2020.1782335>
- Khan, M. A., et al. (2019). Institutional quality and financial development: The United States perspective. *Journal of Multinational Financial Management*, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mulfin.2019.01.001>
- Khan, M. A., et al. (2020). Asymmetric Impact of Institutional Quality on Tourism Inflows Among Selected Asian Pacific Countries. *Sustainability*, 12(3), 1223, <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12031223>
- Kutan, A. M., et al. (2017). Does Institutional Quality Matter for Financial Development and Growth? Further Evidence from MENA Countries. *Australian Economic Papers*, 56(3), 228-248, <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8454.12097>
- Levine, R. (1997). Financial development and economic growth: views and agenda. *Journal of economic literature*, 35(2), 688-726, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/2729790>

- Liargovas, P. G., & Skandalis, K. S. (2012). Foreign direct investment and trade openness: The case of developing economies. *Social Indicators Research*, 106(2), 323-331, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11205-011-9806-9>
- Liu, H., et al. (2020). Does financial deepening attract foreign direct investment? Fresh evidence from panel threshold analysis. *Research in International Business and Finance*, 101198, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ribaf.2020.101198>
- Liu, T. (2008). Impact of regional trade agreements on Chinese foreign direct investment. *Chinese Economy*, 41(5), 68-102, <https://doi.org/10.2753/CES1097-1475410504>
- Majeed, A., et al. (2023). The Impact of Social Preferences on Supply Chain Performance: An Application of the Game Theory Model. *Complexity*, 2023, 4911514, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2023/4911514>
- Miniesy, R. S., & Elish, E. (2017). Is Chinese outward FDI in MENA little? *Journal of Chinese Economic and Foreign Trade Studies*, 10(1), 19-43, <https://doi.org/10.1108/JCEFTS-09-2016-0026>
- Nkoa, B. E. O. (2018). Determinants of foreign direct investment in Africa: An analysis of the impact of financial development. *Economics Bulletin*, 38(1), 221-233, <https://www.accessecon.com/Pubs/EB/2018/Volume38/EB-18-V38-I1-P23.pdf>
- Noorbakhsh, F., et al. (2001). Human capital and FDI inflows to developing countries: New empirical evidence. *World Development*, 29(9), 1593-1610, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0305-750X\(01\)00054-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0305-750X(01)00054-7)
- Otchere, I., et al. (2016). FDI and financial market development in Africa. *The World Economy*, 39(5), 651-678, <https://doi.org/10.1111/twec.12277>
- Rahman, M. M., et al. (2017). Impact of Cost Efficiency on Bank Capital and the Cost of Financial Intermediation: Evidence from BRICS Countries. *International Journal of Financial Studies*, 5(4), 32, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijfs5040032>
- Rauf, A., et al. (2018). Energy and Ecological Sustainability: Challenges and Panoramas in Belt and Road Initiative Countries. *Sustainability*, 10(8), 2743, <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10082743>
- Rousseau, P. L., & Wachtel, P. (2011). What is happening to the impact of financial deepening on economic growth? *Economic inquiry*, 49(1), 276-288, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1465-7295.2009.00197.x>
- Sachs, J. D. (2018). Geography, geopolitics, and policy in the performance of transition economies. *Economics of Transition*, <https://doi.org/10.1111/ecot.12163>
- Sahay, M. R., et al. (2016). *Rethinking financial deepening: Stability and growth in emerging markets*. International Monetary Fund. <https://www.imf.org/external/pubs/ft/sdn/2015/sdn1508.pdf>

- Saini, N., & Singhania, M. (2018). Determinants of FDI in developed and developing countries: a quantitative analysis using GMM. *Journal of Economic Studies*, 45(2), 348-382, <https://doi.org/10.1108/JES-07-2016-0138>
- Sarafidis, V., & Wansbeek, T. (2012). Cross-sectional dependence in panel data analysis. *Econometric Reviews*, 31(5), 483-531, <https://doi.org/10.1080/07474938.2011.611458>
- Silva, S. H. R. d., et al. (2017). Economic growth, volatility and their interaction: What's the role of finance? *Economic Systems*, 41(3), 433-444, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecosys.2016.10.008>
- Soong, J.-J. (2016). The Political Economy of Development Between China and the ASEAN States: Opportunity and Challenge. *The Chinese Economy*, 49(6), 395-399, <https://doi.org/10.1080/10971475.2016.1207972>
- Soto, M. (2009). System GMM estimation with a small sample. *Barcelona Economics Working Paper Series*, <https://ddd.uab.cat/record/69615>
- Soumaré, I., & Tchana Tchana, F. (2015). Causality between FDI and Financial Market Development: Evidence from Emerging Markets. *The World Bank Economic Review*, 29(suppl_1), S205-S216, <https://doi.org/10.1093/wber/lhv015>
- Sultanuzzaman, M. R., et al. (2019). Effects of export and technology on economic growth: Selected emerging Asian economies. *Economic Research-Ekonomska Istraživanja*, 32(1), 2515-2531, <https://doi.org/10.1080/1331677X.2019.1650656>
- Svirydzenka, K. (2016). Introducing a new broad-based index of financial development. *IMF Working Paper*, WP/16/5, <https://www.imf.org/en/Publications/WP/Issues/2016/12/31/Introducing-a-New-Broad-based-Index-of-Financial-Development-43621>
- Tzeremes, N. (2018). Financial Development and Countries' Production Efficiency: A Nonparametric Analysis. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, 11(3), 46, <https://doi.org/10.3390/jrfm11030046>
- UNCTAD. (2024). *Foreign direct investment: Inward and outward flows and stock, annual* <https://unctadstat.unctad.org/wds/ReportFolders/reportFolders.aspx>
- WDI. (2024). World Development Indicators. <https://databank.worldbank.org/source/world-development-indicators>
- Yahia, Y. E., et al. (2018). The Impact of Foreign Direct Investment on Domestic Investment: Evidence from Sudan. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Issues*, 8(6), 11-20, <https://doi.org/10.32479/ijefi.6895>

Appendix A: Hausman Test to Choose Between Fixed Effect and Random Effect

	Below Threshold RE	Above Threshold RE
Chi ²	53.33	38.00
P	0.0000	0.0000

Appendix B: List of Countries Under Consideration

SN	Country Name	SN	Country Name	SN	Country Name	SN	Country Name
1	Albania	21	Czech Rep.	41	Korea, Rep.	61	Romania
2	Algeria	22	Ecuador	42	Kuwait	62	Russia
3	Armenia	23	Egypt	43	Kyrgyz Republic	63	Rwanda
4	Azerbaijan	24	Estonia	44	Lebanon	64	Saudi Arabia
5	Bahrain	25	Fiji	45	Libya	65	Senegal
6	Bangladesh	26	Finland	46	Madagascar	66	Sierra Leone
7	Barbados	27	France	47	Malaysia	67	Singapore
8	Bhutan	28	Georgia	48	Moldova	68	Slovenia
9	Bolivia	29	Ghana	49	Mongolia	69	South Africa
10	Bosnia and Herzegovina	30	Greece	50	Morocco	70	Sri Lanka
11	Brunei Darussalam	31	Guyana	51	Nepal	71	Tajikistan
12	Bulgaria	32	Hungary	52	New Zealand	72	Thailand
13	Cambodia	33	Indonesia	53	Nigeria	73	Tonga
14	Cameroon	34	Iran	54	Macedonia	74	Tunisia
15	Chile	35	Israel	55	Oman	75	Turkey
16	China	36	Italy	56	Pakistan	76	Ukraine
17	Colombia	37	Jamaica	57	Panama	77	UAE
18	Costa Rica	38	Jordan	58	Philippines	78	Vanuatu
19	Cote d'Ivoire	39	Kazakhstan	59	Poland	79	Vietnam
20	Croatia	40	Kenya	60	Portugal		

COPYRIGHTS

©2025 The Author(s). This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY 4.0), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, as long as the original authors and source are cited. No permission is required from the authors or the publishers.

HOW TO CITE THIS ARTICLE

Islam, M. A., Hassan, M. R. and Hossen, M. M. (2025). Realizing the Threshold Effect of Trade Openness in Finance-FDI Nexus: Evidence from Belt and Road Initiative Countries. *International Journal of Management, Accounting and Economics*, 12 (11), 1697-1719. doi: 10.22034/ijmae.2025.232405

URL: https://www.ijmae.com/article_232405.html

